

ASAP

A Systemic APProach to social media
and pre-adolescents through thinking

ASAP EDUCATIONAL PROGRAMME
LEARNING UNIT

INTRODUCTION

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R3.2.1 ASAP Educational Programme Handbook

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ASAP Educational Programme Handbook

Introduction

Today, educators face the challenge of guiding preadolescents – children typically aged 11 to 13 – through a world deeply shaped by social media. The ASAP Educational Programme Handbook – or simply the Handbook – was created to support this task by offering concrete tools, reflective pathways, and participatory activities that help young people develop awareness, critical thinking, and emotional literacy in their digital lives.

The Handbook is the main educational outcome of the Erasmus+ project *ASAP – A Systemic Approach to social media and preadolescents through thinking skills education* (www.socialmediakids.eu), co-funded by the European Union. ASAP brings together institutions from Italy, Portugal, Croatia, Slovenia, and the Czech Republic, combining expertise from education, media, psychology, communication, and research to promote a deeper understanding of how digital media influence the growth and wellbeing of preadolescents.

At its core, the ASAP approach integrates thinking skills education into digital and social media literacy. Rather than focusing on the risks of technology, it invites preadolescents to reflect on their thinking, emotions, and relationships – empowering them to act with empathy, autonomy, and responsibility in both digital and physical contexts.

A Flexible Handbook

The ASAP Handbook is designed as a modular and adaptable toolkit. Each Learning Unit (LU) offers a coherent sequence of tested activities that can be used in full or in part, depending on the educator's goals, group composition, and context.

Flexibility means that:

- activities can be delivered in a single session or combined into longer learning paths;
- their order can be rearranged to create customised sequences that better fit the group's dynamics, timing, or learning objectives;
- they can involve children, parents, teachers, or mixed groups;
- they can be adapted to different ages, learning environments, and levels of digital experience.

For instance, an activity designed for classroom dialogue can easily be reimagined for a parent-child discussion at home or adapted into a youth workshop. Each activity includes objectives, timing, materials, and step-by-step guidance – supporting both educators who prefer ready-to-use tools and those who enjoy personalising and reinterpreting the process.

This flexibility supports the creation of learning environments where knowledge and practice, reflection and experience, come together in active, participatory ways.

An Open Resource

The Handbook has been conceived as an open educational resource, continuously evolving through field testing and feedback. It is not a prescriptive or definitive guide, but an invitation to experiment, adapt, and co-create.

Each Learning Unit is replicable, expandable, and adaptable. The identified topics address key issues emerging from the ASAP Desk and Field Research, representing an initial set of pathways to develop social, emotional, and digital competences. Educators are encouraged to extend and modify these pathways according to their local contexts and learners' needs.

Openness also means that educators can build upon the proposed structure to create new Learning Units or activities connected to the overarching theme of digital and social media in the lives of preadolescents. They may integrate insights from their own disciplinary backgrounds or emerging issues from their educational practice, as well as address new challenges that emerge from the constantly evolving digital landscape. In this sense, the Handbook is intended as a living and collaborative framework, capable of growing and transforming alongside the realities it seeks to explore.

This open and participatory approach reflects the dynamic nature of today's educational environments, especially in relation to the fast-changing digital worlds of preadolescents.

The Educational Framework

ASAP's educational approach is rooted in active learning, reflection, and co-construction of meaning. The term *educator* is used throughout the Handbook to highlight the formative rather than didactic nature of the activities: learning happens through dialogue, shared experiences, and collective inquiry, not through one-way transmission of information. Similarly, the term *activity* is preferred over lesson, as the proposed activities are not intended to transmit knowledge in a unidirectional way but to create opportunities for active learning based on dialogue and sharing. The aim is not to provide content to memorise, but to foster the co-construction of meaning, the acquisition of new awareness, and the development of critical, emotional, and relational competences.

The methodology draws inspiration from the European LifeComp and DigComp frameworks – the reference models for the *Personal, Social and Learning to Learn* and the *Digital* key competences for lifelong learning – translating them into accessible and experiential practices. Each Learning Unit connects cognitive, emotional, and social dimensions, helping preadolescents to:

- think critically and creatively;
- understand and manage emotions;
- communicate with empathy and assertiveness;
- evaluate information critically and responsibly;
- recognise and reflect on social influences and digital role models;
- find balance between online and offline life.

How the Handbook is Organised

The ASAP Educational Programme Handbook consists of seven documents: this Introduction and six Learning Units. Each LU explores a key dimension of personal, social, emotional, and digital development, offering structured yet adaptable activities for preadolescents, teachers, and parents. Together, they form a coherent path that combines reflection, creativity, and collaboration.

Each Learning Unit follows a consistent internal structure, which includes target groups, key competences, learning outcomes, phases, activities, and evaluation tools, as well as detailed step-by-step activity plans with corresponding materials and worksheets. This shared format ensures both coherence and ease of use across different educational contexts.

Below is a brief overview of the six Learning Units to guide educators in choosing where to start and how to connect them.

1. The Power of Questions: Unlocking Curiosity and Critical Thinking

Asking good questions is the foundation of understanding. This unit emphasises inquiry and metacognition as tools for growth. Participants learn to distinguish between open and closed questions, explore the link between thought and action, and cultivate creative questioning. By strengthening their ability to ask insightful questions, preadolescents develop critical thinking and problem-solving skills that help them face challenges with curiosity and confidence.

2. Emotions: Understanding Ourselves and Others

Recognising, understanding, and managing emotions is essential – especially in the emotionally charged world of social media. Through reflective games and collaborative activities, participants explore their feelings, practice empathy, and learn to express emotions constructively. This unit helps preadolescents build resilience and supportive relationships, both online and face-to-face.

3. Communication: Building Bridges with Empathy and Assertiveness

Effective communication is at the heart of healthy relationships. This unit focuses on active listening, empathy, and assertive self-expression. Through role-playing and perspective-taking, preadolescents learn to express opinions confidently, respect others' viewpoints, and manage conflicts constructively – skills that strengthen both online and offline interactions.

4. Authenticity and Authority: Unmasking Misinformation

In a world overflowing with information, evaluating credibility is crucial. This unit introduces critical media literacy, helping participants distinguish facts from opinions and identify misinformation. By analysing content and practising fact-checking, preadolescents become more discerning and responsible digital citizens, able to contribute to a culture of informed engagement.

5. Role Models: Shaping Values in the Digital Age

Role models – whether online influencers or people in everyday life – strongly affect young people's values and behaviours. This unit guides participants to reflect on these influences, understand the risks and benefits of online trends, and recognise how social expectations shape their choices. By doing so, they strengthen self-awareness and learn to act according to their own values.

6. Onlife: Finding Balance in a Digital World

The blending of online and offline experiences into a single, integrated reality – the onlife dimension – brings new challenges and opportunities. This unit helps participants explore their digital footprints, reflect on balance in daily routines, and create shared agreements for healthy digital habits. Educators, parents, and students alike gain tools to build intentional, responsible, and balanced relationships with technology.

Closing Note

Though separated documents, the six Learning Units are not isolated modules but interconnected steps in a shared learning journey. They move from questioning and self-awareness to communication, media literacy, and digital balance – guiding both educators and learners toward a systemic understanding of life in the digital age.

Through experiential learning, reflection, and collaboration, the Handbook encourages intergenerational dialogue between children, parents, and educators, helping each to see the digital world not as a separate space, but as an integral part of human experience.

Reflection and self-assessment are at the heart of this process: every activity becomes a moment to pause, observe, and grow individually and together.

More than a sheer guide, the ASAP Handbook is an invitation to explore, adapt, and co-create educational pathways that nurture curiosity, empathy, and responsibility. It calls on educators to cultivate spaces where thinking, feeling, and acting converge – helping the next generation to live fully, both online and onlife.

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